

Producing Mushrooms in Oak Woods

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Ectomycorrhizal fungus of the genus *Boletus* in oak woods

Oak forests are very diverse ecosystems offering favourable conditions for the development of fungi, including several species of mushrooms of gastronomic interest. Wild mushrooms stand out for their diversity, their importance in agroforestry production and their numerous applications in the pharmaceutical, biotechnological and food industries, that can also represent a source of income that complements wood production. From an ecological point of view, the mushrooms that grow in oak forests are grouped into mycorrhizal and saprophytic. Mycorrhizal fungi establish symbiotic associations with tree roots, providing them with a better capacity to explore and utilise soil resources, greater protection against pathogens and tolerance to drought, while the fungi receive the nutrients necessary for their survival and fruiting. Saprophytes work by decomposing organic matter, recycling and incorporating nutrients into the soil and controlling pathogens mainly specialized in broking the cellulose and hemicellulose organic compounds. Although most commercially valuable mushrooms are ectomycorrhizal fungi, saprophytic species also grow in oak forests, especially in areas where organic matter accumulates. Forest management plays a crucial role in the development of mushrooms, directly influencing their diversity and productivity. Practices such as tree thinning, pruning and undergrowth clearing alter the conditions of light, humidity and soil composition, affecting the habitats where fungi thrive. However, inappropriate interventions, such as excessive removal of organic matter or soil compaction, may jeopardise fungal diversity and reduce the economic potential of mushrooms. Management practices should therefore prioritise soil protection, promoting the conservation of inoculum sources and the diversity of fungal communities, with special attention to the habitats of gastronomically valued species.

Eduardo Pousa(1), Ana Carolina Farias(1), João Paulo Castro(2), Marina Castro(2)

(1) Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal

(2) CIMO, LA SusTEC, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança. Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal

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